

Complete

Cooperate for Open Survey

February 18, 2021 11:09 AM MST

Q4 - What potential benefits of cooperation with other open access publications interest

you the most? Below, we've grouped some potential answers into broad categories.

Please select all that apply; subsequent questions will allow you to get more specific

within each of these categories. Don't feel constrained by what's here! You can also offer

your own ideas in the free response field.

#	Field	Choice Count
75	Knowledge sharing	32.81% 42
76	Labor sharing	16.41% 21
77	Cooperatively sourced funding	22.66% 29
78	Cooperatively owned tools and infrastructure	19.53% 25
79	If none of the above broad categories is applicable, please tell us what other benefits of cooperation interest you:	8.59% 11

Showing rows 1 - 6 of 6

Q4_79_TEXT - If none of the above broad categories is applicable, please tell us what ot...

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Enhanced visibility for the work

Raising visibility/awareness about open access

Things like access to DOIs, etc.

We don't have a copyeditor. Co-funding a position like that would be especially terrific.

We're well established and have solved most of these issues within our very significant constraints. What would make a difference is being able to effectively lobby to get our journal listed in various databases and rating systems. Even the DOAJ has now become so labour-intensive to get recognised in that we do not have the capacity to do so.

Spreading the costs of publication across several publications, with shared people or infrastructure seems like a great idea but hard to implement.

Popularization of scholarly publications

Creating strong bonds and voices for responsible OA publishing also vis-à-vis established publishers

Dialogue with other editors / managers would be useful

To develop shared standards of ethical review process. Write guidelines together. Discuss them annually (or so) and communicate to the audience that our standards are a product of collaborative work across many journals. Establishing a network of strong OA journals would also increase our credibility. If we can communicate that we develop and share the same high peer-review standards, that we collaboratively develop the procedures of running ethical OA journals, this could be a real game changer. Some OA journals are one/two-person projects, or are linked to research grants and thus might appear as rather ephemeral initiatives which rise and fall with individuals. I find it would be critical to have a strong network of OA journals to make clear that we are part of a large-scale change in academia and we are the its forefront, developing collectively new standards.

I would need to discuss with the other editors of the journal I co-edit about other possibilities.

Q5 - In terms of knowledge sharing, what interests you most?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Knowledge sharing among all members of a cooperative	39.22% 20
2	Knowledge sharing within cohorts of similar publications	56.86% 29
3	Other:	3.92% 2
		51

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Q5_3_TEXT - Other:

Other:

The priority concern is to make the articles in the journal freely available to the GENERAL PUBLIC, including students

We are willing to share know-how and experience. Occasionally we can share China related content with similar publications.

Q6 - In terms of labor sharing, what interests you most?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Web development and metrics support	14.86% 11
2	Copyediting, proofing, and other production support	21.62% 16
3	Discoverability and metadata support	21.62% 16
4	Preservation and archiving support	10.81% 8
5	Visibility and social media support	17.57% 13
6	Other:	1.35% 1
7	Multilingual and translation support	12.16% 9
		74

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Q6_6_TEXT - Other:

Other:

Language support

Q7 - In terms of cooperatively sourced funding, what interests you most?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Shared revenue model	64.52% 20
2	Other:	35.48% 11

31

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Q7_2_TEXT - Other:

Other:

Shared sustenance model! We're a non-profit and run on a grant.

Open Library of Humanities models

reducing the costs of publication--- and making sure that people are paid respectable living wages to do the work that generally, academics don't or aren't qualified to do.

Shared fundraising possibilities for philanthropic support to offset operating costs, reduce APCs etc.

Applying funding together for shared work; I don't know if this is what "revenue model" means

Cooperatively get funding to further develop the OA model from large funding schemes, e.g. EU

Also perhaps a shared infrastructure for library partnership models a la OLH. Perhaps the new OA Switchboard will evolve to support something like this, where funders can support multiple journals/publishers.

Sustainability is one of our biggest concerns. Any model that would help ensure our long term survivability, and that of others, is attractive

As a no-cost open-access journal editor revenue (from users) isn't on the radar, any form of funding support would definitely be of interest

But I was rather thinking of something like shared advocacy for OA to facilitate our individual applications for funding in our respective countries. I think it would be really cool to have a person or two who would knock on doors and introduce us as a whole package to librarians, for example.

Other:

Exercise pressure on public institutions (universities, research centre) to obtain funding to sustain OA initiatives and create ad hoc job positions (e.g. for web developers, digital managers, social media experts etc)

Q8 - In terms of cooperatively owned tools and infrastructure, what interests you most?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Shared reviewer database	14.29% 6
2	Shared publishing platform	35.71% 15
3	Searchable portal of publications, with each on its own platform	35.71% 15
4	Other	14.29% 6

42

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Q8_4_TEXT - Other

Other

DOIs, other support with indexing in classic catalogues

Not a shared platform is in co-publishing -- but working with journals who use the same platform (e.g., OJS) and can therefore problem-solve together.

Much more improved OJS capabilities, or jumping ship to a stronger platform where we can crowdsource solutions and maybe (gasp!) share a fulltime developer to improve the sites

Our journal desperately needs a professional, functional journal management system for handling submissions, allocation of reviewers, communication with authors, internal communication, etc. This exceeds the expertise of our university IT department but is a service that, if purchased, would involve real expenses.

Coordination of skilled people who can offer services to multiple publications. We only need a fifth or a third of a managing editor to do what we do, but we would want some kind of professional relationship with that person. So coordinating that and setting expectations is part of what I imagine as a shared collaboration infrastructure.

Other

We publish on PubPub, and doubt that a reviewer database would be too helpful, given the disparate topics. The searchable portal would make sense. Especially helpful would be the kind of backend/workflow tool, of the sort that COPIM is working on.

End of Report